

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Livelihood

Profitability of urea supergranules in rice

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We compared the economics of N applied as urea supergranule (USG) and as prilled urea (PU) at three N levels in field experiments 1985 and 1986 wet seasons, in a randomized block design with four replications. Experimental soil was silt loam, classified as Aquic Hapludoll. The site lies about 30 km south of the Shivalik range of the Himalayas, 29° N, 79°29' E,

Comparative economics of USC placement and PU split application.^a Uttar Pradesh, India, 1985 and 1986.

Item	N rate (kg/ha)		
	29	58	87
Labor d/ha for USG placement	8	10	10
Wages (\$/d)	1.21	1.21	1.21
Total labor cost/ha for USG placement (\$)	9.68	12.10	12.10
Incremental yield (t/ha) from USG	0.40	0.80	1.00
Added value of rice ^b (\$)	44.80	89.60	112.00
Labor d/ha for basal application of PU	2	2	2
Labor d/ha for top-dressing of PU	1	1	1
Total labor d/ha for PU application	3	3	3
Total labor cost for PU (\$)	3.63	3.63	3.63
Difference in labor cost (USG-PU) (\$)	6.05	8.47	8.47
Difference in material cost (USG-PU) (\$)	1.08	2.15	3.22
Total additional cost (\$)	7.13	10.62	11.69
Additional return from USG (\$)	37.67	78.98	100.31

^aMean of 1985 and 1986. ^bPrice of rough rice = \$112.00/t.

and is a subtropical, subhumid climatic zone.

Rice cultivar Pant Dhan 4 was transplanted (45-d-old seedlings) at 20 × 20-cm spacing 15 Jul both years. PKZn (18 kg P, 33 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha) was broadcast and incorporated 1 d before transplanting (DBT). USG was placed 8-10 cm deep 1 d after transplanting in the middle of every four hills. PU was applied 1/2 broadcast and incorporated 1 DBT, 1/4 topdressed at tillering, and 1/4

topdressed 5-7 d before panicle initiation. All costs were the same except for N.

Prices were \$112/t for rough rice, \$0.37/kg N for PU, and \$0.41/kg N for USG. Cost of N application was estimated as \$1.21/labor d, with 3 labor d/ha for PU and 8-10 labor d/ha for USG.

Increased yield with USG compensated for additional costs of application (see table). □

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Training and technology transfer research

Information gaps in transmitting rice recommendations to farmers

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Technological innovations in rice culture are usually transmitted to farming communities through extension recommendations. A recommendation will contain a certain amount of information that farmers can use to improve their productivity.

In many instances, however, we find an information gap. Information gap refers to the amount of information contained in the information input, but not in the information output.

The Training and Visit (T & V) System of Agricultural Extension is an extension management tool. Special

attention has been given to its implementation in the rice subsector of Sri Lanka. The T & V System is organized to disseminate information from research stations through extension to farmers, and vice versa.

We focused on selected rice recommendations given by the T & V System. This study reports the intensity of information gaps. Data were collected in one wet zone district of southern Sri Lanka during the major rice-growing season, Sep 1986-Feb 1987.

Subject Matter Officers (SMOs) and Agricultural Officers (AOs) of the district were interviewed. Their extension recommendations were considered as information input. Information items were extracted from selected recommendations and standard scores computed. A sample of 100 farmers were surveyed to obtain the information output.

On varietal recommendation, the information gap is low (see table). For preseeding treatments and chemical weed control recommendations, information gaps are higher; the knowledge acquired by farmers is insufficient. The variation in the information gap could be due to the fact that varietal recommendations were introduced some years ago, and extension efforts to popularize them have been continuous. The recommendations are simple and seeds are a low-cost innovation that farmers can practice with low capital outlay. Even though preseed treatment recommendations are low-cost innovations, some are too complex for the farmers' technical competence.

Information gap for different recommendations. Sri Lanka, 1986-87.

Recommendation	Information input (Extension specialists' score)	Information output (Farmers' score)	Information gap (%)
High-yielding rice varieties	3.0	2.5	17
Preseeding treatments	7.0	4.0	43
Chemical weed control	5.0	3.1	38

Weed control recommendations are high-cost innovations and, due to commercial competition, a large number of chemicals are available on the retail market. These factors do not have a positive impact on farmers' information output, resulting in higher information gaps.

The T & V System utilizes serial communication. The recommendations

that ultimate users receive pass through many communicators. Hence, this system may be more appropriate for transmitting information about simple, low-cost innovations. To reduce the information gaps observed with complex recommendations, alternate methodologies (training classes, demonstrations, etc.) may need to be intensified. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

IRTP now INGER

The International Rice Testing Program, established in 1975, has become the International Network for Genetic Enhancement of Rice (INGER), effective 1 Jul 1989. INGER is a component of a new project, the International Cooperative Rice Improvement Project for Sustainable Rice Farming, which is funded by the United Nations Development Programme and coordinated by IRRI. The network is the world's largest for agricultural research: scientists from more than 70 countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America participate.

New IRRI publications

Bacterial blight of rice
Progress in irrigated rice research
Research highlights for 1988